

Impact of Intellectual Capital on the Small and Medium Enterprises' Innovation Activities in South-West Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the Impact of Intellectual Capital on the Innovation activities of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). The specific objective determined the effect of human capital on product innovation and assessed the impact of structural capital on process innovation. It also examined the effect of relational capital on service innovation. The population of the study consisted of twenty-three thousand, two hundred and ninety (23,290) registered SMEs located in South-West Nigeria. The sample consisted of 393 SMEs drawn from the population using a multi-stage sampling technique. Structured questionnaires were employed to collect data from business owners and managers of the selected SMEs in the manufacturing and services sectors. The data were analysed using linear and multiple regression with the aid of SPSS 24. Findings from the study indicate that all three dimensions of intellectual capital – human, structural and relational- have a positive and significant effect on SME products, processes, and service innovation activities. The study concluded that SMES must utilise its intellectual capital to improve its capacities for innovation, thereby enhancing its level of competitiveness.

Keywords: *Intellectual Capital, Innovation Activities, Small and Medium Enterprises.*

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Introduction

The impactful role of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in sustainable economic growth has been recognised and acknowledged by scholars, researchers, economists, policymakers and entrepreneurs across the world. A growing number of studies have attested to the SME sector as the driving force of nations' economic growth and development, making up over 90% of business organisations in both developed and emerging economies (Kuruvilla & Harikumar, 2018; Abodunde *et al.*, 2020). Given the extent of their economic activities, SMEs play a leading role in job creation and increasingly serve as sources of new ideas (Hilmola *et al.*, 2015).

Many studies, including Ndesaulwa (2016), Katarzyna (2016), and Park (2019), affirm that the economy globally has moved from an industry-based economy to a knowledge-based economy. This paradigm shift has been attributed to the rapid evolution of the business environment that has witnessed rapid technological advancements, the increasing pace of globalisation and hyper-competition, the shorter product life-cycle, the changing customer preferences, expectations and awareness (Adeyemo *et al.*, 2020). In recent times, the SME sector around the globe has found it extremely difficult to constantly achieve targeted business objectives due to the unpredictable and dynamic environment, open market

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competition and the devastation of the COVID-19 pandemic. According to Ogunleye et al. (2021), this unpalatable scenario has forced entrepreneurs and managers to devise strategies that will enable organisations to remain competitive and remain stronger in a cut-throat global competitive and unpredictable business environment. Among these strategies is innovativeness by Small and Medium Enterprises. To succeed and remain viable, organisations must implement strategies that incorporate creativity and innovativeness. It implies that organisations should embark on creating new products or improve on the existing ones, ensuring its process, organisational and service activities. Innovative innovation is the crucial survival strategy of organisations, especially SMEs (Ngah *et al.*, 2022).

In Nigeria, government efforts to foster innovation have been primarily focused on the activities of large firms and innovation-related organisations, such as higher education institutions and research centres that are richly endowed with innovation resources and capabilities. It indicates that the small and medium enterprises (SMEs), which are bedrocks of innovation ecosystems, are often schemed acts of those efforts (Andras *et al.*, 2023). The calls for innovative actions notwithstanding, the level of innovation in Nigeria could be much better (Adeyemo et al., 2020). The country and, by extension, SMEs place less emphasis on innovation for global competitiveness. The Global Innovation Index, Dutta (2022) ranking produced by the World Economic Forum indicated that Nigeria ranked 114th in the world behind great innovators such as Switzerland, the United States of America, Sweden, the United Kingdom and the Netherlands. In Africa, the country lags behind South Africa, Morocco, Tunisia, Kenya, Ghana and Namibia. This condition indicates that business enterprises in Nigeria still need to gain a competitive advantage over other competitors. This competitive disadvantage has led to reduced corporate income, lower government revenue, and access to financial markets. Nigeria's SMEs need to catch up to the innovation frontiers and need help to adopt new technologies and international knowledge flows.

SMEs in Nigeria

Small and Medium Enterprises are found to contribute significantly to employment generation and economic growth in Nigeria (National Bureau of Statistics, 2021). SMEDAN-NBS 2021 Report indicated that there are 39.7 million Micro, Small and Medium enterprises in Nigeria. 38.4 million are micro-enterprises, representing 96.9% of the total, and 1.2 million are SMEs, representing 3.1% of the total.

Due to the need for adequate innovative systems, only a small number of SMEs are able to compete in the international markets. The setback is a result of the high costs of doing business and the rejection of substandard products. Thongyai & Potipiroon (2022) report that research reveals that in their attempt to survive, several SMEs have adopted new technologies and innovations (Akpan *et al.*, 2020) as well as marketing and process innovations (El Charani *et al.*, 2022) while also digitising their sales (Priyono *et al.*, 2020).

Concept of Intellectual Capital

Intellectual capital has attracted prominent attention as a result of the development of the new economy that is powered by information and knowledge (Khalique & Isa, 2014; Osibanjo et al., 2014). Accordingly, researchers and practitioners have recognised intellectual capital as a veritable resource that propels organisations to sustainable competitiveness (Orugun & Aduke, 2017; Omerzel & Jurdana, 2016).

The concept of intellectual capital has been defined in diverse ways, leading to a need for more agreement regarding its definition and components (Wang et al., 2014). Edvinson (1997) define intellectual capital as the possession of knowledge, applied experience, organisational technology, customer relationships and professional skills that provide the firm with a competitive edge in the marketplace. Edvinson (1997) divided intellectual capital into human capital and structural capital. Stewart (1997) submits that intellectual capital includes knowledge, information, intellectual property and experience that can be leveraged to create wealth. He notes that intellectual capital consists of human, structural, and customer capital.

Hsu & Sabherwal (2011) view intellectual capital as the same as the concept of 'knowledge capital' or 'knowledge assets' defined as the sum of all knowledge utilised by the firms to achieve competitive advantage. The sum of all knowledge refers to knowledge that exists at various levels, whether individual,

organisational or network levels, from inside and outside of firms (Mills & Smith, 2011). Studies show that intellectual capital is regarded as a set of intangibles comprising resources, capabilities and competencies that enhance performance and value creation (Subramanian & Youndt, 2005; Khalique & Isa, 2014).

Intellectual capital is also regarded as a crucial resource for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) (Mariana et al., 2023), as the knowledge, experience, and skills of the owners and employees drive their success. This assertion was further stressed by Supeno et al. (2015) that SMEs require strategic resources to improve their performance and competitiveness. Ngah *et al.* (2022) suggest that SMEs can take advantage of their know-how through innovative intelligence to convert the implicit knowledge into product and process innovation. SMEs can compete on the basis of their know-how, expertise, tradecraft, skills, ideas, intuition and insights (Desouza & Awazu, 2006). This, according to Sylva *et al.* (2016), will result in increased efficiencies in operations and higher rates of successful innovation.

Dimensions of Intellectual Capital

Human Capital

Human capital is the combined knowledge, skill, innovativeness and ability of the organisation's individuals to meet the tasks at hand (Tongo & Tongo, 2021). It also includes wisdom, spirituality, experience, intuition and latent talents of the employees. Human capital is the most influential aspect of intellectual capital (Tarus & Sitienei, 2015; Barkat & Beh, 2018). It is the property of the employee as it is not yet owned by the organisation (Abdulaali, 2018). It helps the business enterprise to respond to environmental changes innovatively. Human capital can create wealth by helping in the innovation activities of the organisation. According to Adeyemo (2021), human capital consists of education, experience, training, intelligence, energy, work habits, trust and initiative possessed by an employee. Aljuboori et al. (2021) submit that as an intangible resource for the organisation, human capital is an important element in the process of transforming information into valuable knowledge that will improve an organisation's innovative performance. Modern business managers must be able to locate and exploit all forms of human capital in order to create future organisational wealth. The managers must provide the right incentives that would motivate individuals who own different brands of human capital to release them for the purpose of generating future wealth for business enterprises to enhance greater achievement.

According to Tongo & Tongo (2021), motivating employees to share their tacit human capital should be approached from two levels, which are the personal and organisational levels. Business enterprises invest a lot of money and time to ensure that they employ the right calibre of personnel. Similarly, they spend much money on training and development in a bid to equip their employees with adequate knowledge, skills, and the right attitude to work. A motivated knowledge seller will unveil his or her hidden knowledge without being pushed, threatened or compelled to do so by his or her superiors. For effective management and utilisation of human capital, contemporary organisations must be committed to a corporate philosophy that recognises knowledge work as the engine of the enterprises, focusing on a business culture that promotes creativity and innovation at all levels of the organisation. While managers are in charge of creating an organisational climate in which innovation can occur, the knowledge and skills of employees often assist in the success of innovation (Dabie *et al.*, 2018)

Human capital is one of the dimensions of intellectual capital that has a major contribution to the company's strategic decisions and has an important role to play in the context of SMEs (Supriyanto *et al.*, 2022). Human capital refers to an employee's competence, knowledge, training, skills, innovation, attitude, community, wisdom, experience, capability, innovation, creativity, entrepreneurial spirit and leadership.

A firm's resources are made up of assets, capabilities, processes, attributes, information and knowledge (Barney, 1991). These resources must be valuable, inimitable, non-substitutable and non-transferable (Barney, 1991) in order to enhance a sustainable competitive advantage. Human capital presents the knowledge, capacities, and abilities of individuals that are incorporated into the organisation's resources (Nieves & Quintana, 2018).

Human capital is regarded as a veritable tool for innovation (Jibir & Abdu, 2021). In order to be innovative, firms desire certain qualities of human capital (Beltramino *et al.*, 2022). The workforce requires human capital to be creative, bright, skilful, and experts in their roles and functions, as well as contributions of new ideas and knowledge. It has been asserted that if organisations have human resources with a high degree of knowledge, skill and experience, they can adapt to greater flexibility in acquiring new knowledge with a more improved capability to innovate (Subramanian & Youndt, 2005; Nieves & Quintana, 2018; Beltramino *et al.*, 2022). The greater the stock of human capital, the greater the opportunities to exchange and combine knowledge and the greater the capacity for innovation (Ali *et al.*, 2021). The literature supported the existence of a significant positive relationship between human capital and a firm's ability to innovate (Bekeev, 2020).

Structural Capital

Once enterprises are successful in motivating employees to unleash their human capital, they become the owners of this form of capital (Tongo & Tongo, 2021). At this point, human capital is transformed into structural capital. Hence, structural capital is owned by the business enterprises. Unlike human capital, structural capital can be traded, stored and processed by organisations. It is the value that remains with a company after individuals are no longer in its employment (Fenyves *et al.*, 2018).

Structural capital is associated with the policies, social values, cultural artefacts processes, procedures, databases, patents, trademark manuals, hierarchical structures, technologies, rules and regulations of corporate entities (Barkat & Beh, 2018). It includes everything else in the organisation's capabilities that support individuals' productivity through the sharing and transmission of knowledge, research and development, information systems and laboratories. Structural capital helps in the development of the infrastructure that human capital needs in the creation of values for the organisation (Xu *et al.*, 2019). According to Menzies *et al.* (2020), a structural capital that promotes a collaborative attitude among employees in decision-making and their interactiveness with various knowledge structures is a catalyst for greater capacity for innovation.

Relational Capital

Relational capital is that component of intellectual capital that is often referred to as customer capital or social capital. It represents the value embedded in the relationship between the firm and its customers. Also, it refers to market capital, which signifies the market and trade relationships that the organisation holds with its customers and suppliers within the global markets. Relational capital consists of the knowledge embedded in and derived from relationships with different stakeholders, including suppliers, distributors, shareholders and partners (Edvinsson & Malone, 1997).

Concept of Innovation

Innovation is defined as a new product or service, a new production process technology, a new structure or administrative system, or a new plan or program pertaining to organisational members. Schumpeter (1934) defines innovation as the introduction of new goods, the introduction of a new production method, the opening of a new market, or the opening of a new source of supply. In the same view, Adeyemo (2021) see innovation as an ongoing process of exclusion, search, and exploration that results in new products, new techniques, new organisational forms, and new markets. OECD (2005) defines innovation as an activity that produces new or significant marketing methods or business organisations. Innovation also refers to the process of creating ideas, developing an invention and introducing a new product, process or service to the market (Sombolayuk & Yusuf, 2019).

Product innovation refers to the introduction of new products or services in order to create a new market or customers (Wang & Ahmed, 2004). Product innovation requires varied organisational strategies as well as unique inputs, which results in novel output (Saez-Martinez *et al.*, 2016). Product innovation is usually the result of the production and commercialisation of new goods or with improved performance characteristics.

Process innovation can be defined as changes in the ways of producing or developing products, including new logistics, new raw materials, new production lines, new production processes/methods, and new technology. Process innovation is very important in a firm's manufacturing process as it gives it an advantage over its competitors.

Innovation in services sectors differs significantly from innovation in many manufacturing sectors as it is less technological, more incremental and often less formally organised. Through a systematic review, Witell *et al.* (2016) examine divergent perspectives of service innovation and identify unique and shared characteristics in definitions of service innovation. Service innovation is viewed as a new development in activities undertaken to deliver core service products for various reasons, such as making those core service products more attractive to users. It is an offering not previously available to a firm's customers resulting from additions to or changes in the services concept (Cheng & Krumwiede, 2017). According to Shelton (2009), service innovation consists of a manufacturer's engagement in various innovation activities to enhance customers' satisfaction, which includes after-sales services, warranty policy, maintenance routines, and order placement systems.

Innovative service results in the extent to which the firm integrates new knowledge into service offerings, which directly or indirectly results in value for the firm and its customers (Salunke *et al.*, 2019). Service innovation, in the view of Aas *et al.* (2017), is a new service experience or service solution comprising one or several of the following dimensions: a new service concept, new customer interaction, new value system/business partners, new revenue mode or new organisational or technological service delivery system. Developing services has become a new strategy for firms across different industries, and innovative services have emerged as a strategy for achieving a sustainable competitive advantage (Saqib & Satar, 2021).

Empirical Review

Rideg *et al.* (2023) investigated the relationship between intellectual capital components and innovation using a sample of 1243 Hungarian small and medium-sized enterprises. The results reveal a significantly positive effect of structural capital and relational capital on innovation using logistic regression analysis.

The role of intellectual capital in process and product innovation among SMEs in an emerging country was analysed by Beltramino *et al.* (2022). The sample consisted of 259 industrial SMEs from Cordoba, Argentina. The data were analysed using partial least squares-structural equation modelling (PSL-SEM). Findings from the study provided empirical evidence showing that the three components of intellectual capital generated a positive and significant effect on innovation.

Adegoriola studied the effect of innovation on the performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) (2021). Findings from the study showed that product innovation has a significant relationship with SME performance.

Theoretical Framework

A number of studies have linked resource-based theory, knowledge-based theory, and dynamic capabilities to firms' innovation activities. The underpinning theory of this current study is the Dynamic Capabilities theory. The choice of this theory is anchored on the fact that the theory advocates a combination of resources, capabilities, and competencies to achieve equivalence with the changing business environment. Teece *et al.* (1997) argue that for companies to achieve success in the global market, they must demonstrate rapid responsiveness to market changes and prompt product innovation. The literature on intellectual capital management suggests that it is a crucial resource for knowledge creation and the attainment of sustainable competitive advantages. Intellectual capital represents a source of creativity and innovation for organisations (Tongo & Tongo, 2021). In their decision-making processes, business managers rely on intellectual capital deployment for strategic implementation focus in order to take advantage of their dynamic and intangible intellectual assets (Adeyemo, 2021).

Teece et al. (1997) argue that the competencies of the firm must change in response to environmental change and that the success of this change is closely related to the firm's ability to initiate and guide a dynamic and uncertain process.

Conceptual Framework

Having reviewed both theoretical and empirical studies, it is expected that intellectual capital dimensions will have direct link to SMEs innovation activities.

Independent Variables

Dependent Variables

Figure 1. Conceptual Model
Source: Designed by Researcher

Base on the reviewed literature, we formulate the following hypotheses.

H₀₁: Human capital does not significantly affect SMEs' product innovation activity.

H₀₂: Structural capital has no significant impact on SMEs' process innovation activity.

H₀₃: Relational capital does not significantly affect SMEs' service innovation activity.

H₀₄: Intellectual capital dimensions do not jointly impact significantly on SMEs' innovation indicators.

Research Model and Methodology

Research Design

A descriptive and cross-sectional survey research design was used for this study, which enabled the observation of the phenomenon in a completely natural and unchanged environment.

Study Area

The development of small and medium enterprises in Nigeria represents attempts to achieve a broader socio-economic objective (Adeyemo, 2021). The study considered SMEs in the six states of South-West Nigeria, namely Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo and Ekiti States.

South-West Nigeria was chosen due to the cosmopolitan nature of the zone. The majority of the SMEs are in the south, with Lagos, Ogun, Osun, and Oyo states accounting for a significant portion of the total in Nigeria (NBS-SMEDAN, 2017). As a result of these states' populations, urbanisation, nearness to sea, airports, and some cultural variations, more economic activities are taking place. This zone alone accounts for 23,290 SMEs in Nigeria. As a result, South-West Nigeria reflects the typical Nigeria business environment and the characteristics that can shape the economy of the nation.

Population

The population for this study comprised all registered SMEs in South-West Nigeria. Based on the official statistical sources of NBS-SMEDAN (2017), the table below shows the number of registered SMEs in South-West Nigeria.

Table 1. Number of registered SMEs in South-West, Nigeria

States	Small	Medium	Total	Percentage (%)
Ekiti	926	2	928	3.99
Lagos	8,042	354	8,396	36.05
Ogun	2,394	71	2,465	10.58
Ondo	2,324	39	2,363	10.15
Osun	2,995	12	3,007	12.91
Oyo	6,039	92	6,131	26.32
Total	22,720	570	23,290	100.00

Source: SMEDAN/NBS Collaborative Survey: Selected findings, 2017

The populations of 23,290 SMEs are those having their primary business activities in the manufacturing and services sectors.

Sampling Techniques

A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select the enterprises to be included in the study. This is because of the divergence in the composition of the SMEs across sectors and to ensure that the sample is a fair representation of the population. The enterprises were then stratified into small and medium enterprises. A simple random technique was employed to determine the exact number of enterprises taking part in the study. The study employed the statistical formula advanced by Taro Yamane (1967) at a 5% level of significance to obtain an acceptable and reliable statistical sample size, and this produced 393 SMEs as sample size, as stated in Table 3.2 below.

Table 2 Sample size of SMEs in Manufacturing and Service Sectors

Sectors	Ekiti	Lagos	Ogun	Ondo	Osun	Oyo	Total
Manufacturing	4	38	11	10	14	27	104
Services	12	104	30	30	37	76	289
Total	16	142	41	40	51	103	393

Source: Researcher's computation, 2023

Research Instruments

The study used a structured questionnaire to collect data from the respondents, who are mainly managers of the selected SMEs in South-West Nigeria. A structured questionnaire was preferred to ensure standardisation in response gathering and information collection at relatively moderate costs. The questionnaire included five-point Likert-scale psychometric constructs ranging from 5 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree). Every element in the constructs was intended to measure a certain attribute. Furthermore, elements used for the consideration of each of the variables were obtained from prior research whose reliability and validity have been confirmed. They, therefore, present a measure of the reliability of data collection and measurement. The measuring scale for the intellectual capital dimension (human, structural and relational) was adapted from Omerzel & Juardan (2016). The SME innovation activities construct was adapted from Salazar *et al.* (2006).

Reliability of Research Instruments

All items in the questionnaire were subjected to exploratory factor analysis to determine the discriminant validity among the variables. Accordingly, Cronbach's alpha coefficients greater than 0.70 (Razzaq, 2022) were obtained for all the constructs, thereby confirming the reliability of the measuring scales.

Table 3. Discriminant of Validity and Reliability Results

Variables	Items	Factor loadings	Cronbach's alpha
Human Capital	10	Max: 0.692	0.810
		Min: 0.600	
Structural Capital	12	Max: 0.872	0.811
		Min: 0.773	
Relational Capital	12	Max: 0.778	0.768
		Min: 0.0682	
Innovation Constructs	9	Max: 0.870	0.812
		Min: 0.820	

Source: Researcher's computation, 2023

Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive and inferential statistical methods were used to analyse the data collected. Descriptive statistics, which included frequency, percentage weighted mean score and ranking, were employed in the computation and description of the demographic profile of the respondents and the characteristics of the variables of interest in the study. Hypotheses one, two and three were tested using Linear Regression to determine the nature and magnitude of the relationship between the variables. Multiple regression analysis was carried out to determine the magnitude of the joint impact of the independent (human capital, structural capital) on the dependent variable (SMEs' innovation activities measured by product, process and services).

Analysis and Discussion of Findings

A total of 393 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents. Three hundred seventy-three questionnaires were returned, but 13 out of these needed to be properly filled out, leaving 360 duly filled out and completed. The response rate is 91.6%.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents

SMEs Operators (n = 360)		
	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	256	71.3
Female	104	28.7
Years of Experience in Business		
1-5 years	32	8.9
6-10 years	146	40.6
11-15 years	116	32.2
16-20 years	54	15.0
More than 20 years	12	3.3
Position / Title in Business		
Owner / Manager	196	54.4
Functional Manager	164	45.6
Type of Sector		
Manufacturing	96	26.7
Services	264	73.3

Educational Qualification		
SSCE	10	2.7
ND / NCE	24	6.7
HND / BA / B.ED / B.Sc	234	65.0
M.Sc / MA and above	86	24.0
Other forms of education	6	1.6

Table 5. Weighted Mean Scores and Ranking of Respondents Distribution by Extent to which Human Capital affects SMEs Product Innovation

Intellectual Capital (Human Capital)	WMS	Rank
Our employees are highly skilled and widely considered the best in the industry	4.80	1st
Our employees are creative, bright, experts in their particular jobs and functions	4.55	3rd
Our employees are participating in the development of new ideas and knowledge which can successfully be applied to solve organization's problems.	4.52	5th
Our employees undergo training, attend seminars and workshops regularly	4.56	2nd
Our employees have great ability in assessing risks of investments	4.54	4th
Our employees have ability to work in teams, collaborate, interact, debate and share new ideas.	4.45	7th
Our employees are aware of and committed to the company's strategy to be implemented.	4.48	6th

Note: WMS = Weighted Mean Score

From the table above majority of the respondents have highly skilled employees who are considered the best in the industry. The company places emphasis on training and workshop.

Table 6. Weighted Mean Scores and Ranking of Respondents Distribution by Effects of Structural Capital on SMEs Process Innovation

Intellectual Capital (Structural Capital)	WMS	Rank
The atmosphere in this organization is pleasant and members share the same aim to which they feel committed	4.47	2nd
The company has easy and formal mechanisms that guarantee the sharing of best practices among different fields of activities.	4.36	4th
There is great support for innovative ideas in the organization.	4.38	3rd
The organization embeds much of its information in structures and systems making it possible to search for new knowledge.	4.31	8th
Much of the organization's knowledge are coded	4.35	6th
There is access to organization's database and documents / manuals through some kind of networking	4.36	4th
The organization is embedded with latest information technology software to support implementation of strategies	4.34	7th
The organization's structures, systems, procedures and processes support transfer of new knowledge and innovation.	4.55	1st
The organization's culture contains valuable ideas, trust and ways of doing business.	4.30	9th

Note: WMS = Weighted Mean Score

Table 6. above indicates that majority of the firms' structures, systems, procedures and processes support the transfer of new knowledge which propels innovation activity.

Table 7. Weighted Mean Scores and Ranking of Respondents Distribution by Extent to which Relational Capital affects SMEs Service Innovation

Intellectual Capital (Relational Capital)	WMS	Rank
We partner with customers, suppliers, agencies, strategic partners etc to develop solution.	4.58	1st
Our employees are skilled at collaborating with in another to diagnose and solve problems.	4.26	12th

We meet and share experiences with other firms to help us learn.	4.27	11th
Data about customers are continually updated.	4.41	5th
Customers' feed-back is shared across departments in the organization	4.37	7th
There exists organizational mechanism for collaboration with third parties.	4.45	2nd
We create user-centered services that are intuitive, easy to use and meet customers' needs.	4.41	5th
We streamline service delivery processes, reduce wastes and improve productivity.	4.34	8th
We update technology to enhance service experiences, automate tasks and enable new service models.	4.45	2nd
We develop new revenue streams, pricing strategies and partnership to drive growth and profitability.	4.28	10th
We focus on personalization, convenience and delight to build loyalty and advocacy.	4.44	4th
We engage in mobile banking, digital payment, E-commerce and online shopping platforms.	4.34	8th

Note: WMS = Weighted Mean Score

Results from table above show that majority of the organizations partner with major stakeholders. They have organizational mechanism for collaboration and the technology to enhance service delivery. The firms focus is on personalized, convenience and delight to ensure customers satisfaction and loyalty.

Table 8. Weighted Mean Scores and Ranking of Respondents Distribution by SMEs Product Innovation Indicators

SMEs Product Innovation Indicators	WMS	Rank
The company's pioneering character in the introduction of new products is high.	4.72	2nd
The company has been able to introduce new products in the last 2 years.	4.70	1st
A sizeable percentage of the company's annual expense is devoted, for the development of new products.	4.50	3rd

Note: WMS = Weighted Mean Score

Results from the table 9 show that many of the firms have been able to introduce new products into the market, with their pioneering character being high.

Table 9. Weighted Mean Scores and Ranking of Respondents Distribution by SMEs Process Innovation Indicators

SMEs Process Innovation Indicators	WMS	Rank
We are pioneers in the introduction of new processes	4.43	1st
We have introduced a number of new processes in the last two years	4.40	2nd
A sizeable percentage of the company's annual expenses is devoted for the development of new products.	4.23	5th
The structure and systems make it easy to achieve collaboration of people both inside and outside the organization	4.41	3rd
The structure promotes the transfer of new knowledge.	4.35	4th

Note: WMS = Weighted Mean Score

The table 9 above indicated the pioneering attitude of the companies in the introduction of new processes blazing the trail in this area.

Table 10. Weighted Mean Scores and Ranking of Respondents Distribution by SMEs Service Innovation Indicators

SMEs Service Innovation Indicators	WMS	Rank
Customers' patronage has increased in the last few years.	4.54	3rd
Our customers are satisfied with our services.	4.61	1st
We have introduced a number of services innovation that is competitive and effective.	4.55	2nd

Note: WMS = Weighted Mean Score

The results of the table 10 above indicated that with the introduction of some services innovation, most firms have been able to ensure customers' satisfaction resulting in high level of patronage.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Human capital does not significantly affect SMEs product innovation activity.

Table 11. Result of Linear Regression Analysis Showing the Effect of Human Capital on SMEs Product Innovation Activity

Variable	B- value (Coeff.)	Std. Error	T-value	Sig.
Constant	6.672	0.838	7.916	
Human capital	0.286	0.023	13.308***	0.000

Note: ***Significant at 1%; F statistics = 177.049; R² = 0.323 (32.3%)

Source: Survey, 2023

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Structural capital has no significant impact on SMEs Process Innovation activity.

Table 12. Result of Linear Regression Analysis Showing the Impact of Structural Capital on SMEs Process Innovation Activity

Variable	B- value (Coeff.)	Std. Error	T-value	Sig.
Constant	7.714	0.902	8.532	
Structural capital	0.244	0.012	2.091**	0.040

Note: **Significant at 5%; F statistics = 13.100; R² = 0.341 (34.1%)

Source: Survey, 2023

Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: Relational capital does not significantly affect SMEs service innovation activity.

Table 13. Result of Linear Regression Analysis Showing the Effect of Relational Capital on SMEs Service Innovation Activity

Variable	B- value (Coeff.)	Std. Error	T-value	Sig.
Constant	15.768	0.901	17.303	
Relational capital	0.123	0.015	7.259**	0.000

Note: **Significant at 1%; F statistics = 52.826; R² = 0.531 (53.1%)

Source: Survey, 2023

Hypothesis Four

H₀₄: Intellectual capital dimensions (Human, Structural and Relational Capital) do not jointly impact significantly on SMEs Innovation indicators (Product, Process and Service).

Table 14 Result of Multiple Regression Analysis Showing the Joint Effect of Intellectual Capital Variables on SMEs' Innovation Indicators

Variable	B- value (Coeff.)	Std. Error	T-value	Sig.
Constant	12.402	3.652	3.377	
Human Capital	0.792	0.086	9.023***	0.000
Structural Capital	0.291	0.064	4.476***	0.000
Relational Capital	0.168	0.055	2.983***	0.003

Note: ***Significant at 1%; F statistics = 144.938; R² = 0.664 (66.4%)

Source: Survey, 2023

Discussion of Findings

The result of hypothesis one revealed that there is a significant relationship between human capital and product innovation in SMEs. This finding implies that firms having employees who are skilful and knowledgeable with proven competencies will help boost organisations' product innovativeness. The result is in alliance with the findings of Beltramino *et al.* (2022) and Agostini *et al.* (2017), showing a positive and significant relationship between human capital and product innovation.

The result of hypothesis two indicated a positive and significant relationship between structural capital and SMEs' process innovation activity. The finding is in agreement with the studies by Kleim-Paditua *et al.* (2016) and Agostini & Nosella (2017), which established a close connection between the elements of structural capital and process innovation. This finding implies that organisations that embed much of their information in structure systems and procedures would stand a better chance of successful innovative processes. Also, they can complement the knowledge rooted in the skills and experiences of employees with the provision of physical and structural resources to enhance their competencies and capabilities.

In the analysis of the relationship between relational capital and service innovation, we verified that there is a positive and significant relationship between the two variables. This finding is consistent with those of Franco *et al.* (2021) and Dabie *et al.* (2018), who confirmed the relevance of relational capital to innovation with a business network that has a very strong effect.

The fourth objective of this study sought to determine the joint effect of intellectual capital dimensions on SMEs' innovation activities. Results of the hypothesis showed that human, structural and relational capital independently and jointly have positive and significant effects on product, process and service innovation activities of SMEs. This result is in alignment with the findings of Antras *et al.* (2023).

Conclusions

Based on the findings, this study revealed that human capital constitutes a major driver for the implementation of SMEs' Product Innovation activity. The study concludes that human capital is significant and, therefore, plays a pivotal role in the innovative capability of SMEs.

Furthermore, the process innovation of SMEs is highly premised on a well-established structural capital, and this study found it very significant.

The finding established a positive and significant relationship between relational capital and SME service innovation activity. The findings also showed that human capital, structural capital, and relational capital

independently and jointly have significant effects on SME product, process and service innovation activities. Therefore, MSES must utilise its intellectual capital to improve its capacity for innovation and enhance its level of competitiveness.

Contributions to Knowledge

It is hoped that this study contributes to the body of knowledge by bridging some of the gaps in the literature. Previous research on SMEs' innovation activities mainly focused on advanced knowledge-driven economies with particular attention to large and multinational organisations. This study examines an emerging economy with SMEs in focus. This study examines the role of intellectual capital in predicting small and medium enterprises' innovation activities. Our work contributes to the literature showing how, through an intellectual capital strategy, SMEs can improve their capabilities for innovation in products, processes and services.

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